

**INVESTIGATING THE ECONOMIC AND NON-ECONOMIC FACTORS WHICH
EFFECT THE ECONOMIC GROWTH OF KURDISTAN**

Hozan Nayyef Abdulqader
Economic, Kurdistan region of Iraq
hozannayif@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The main purpose of this research is to examine both economic and non-economic factors which effect the economic growth of Kurdistan region of Iraq. The researchers used a quantitative research method to measure developed research hypotheses, the researchers distributed questionnaires to businessmen for several private businesses in Erbil city to measure both economic and non- economic factors that influence their economic growth. However, the researchers gathered 71 questionnaires, all the questions are valid to be analyzed. The findings revealed that concerning the comparing non-economic factors and economic factors, the following results found; there is a strong and positive correlation between economic variables and economic growth, on the other hand there is no correlation between non-economic variables and economic growth in Kurdistan region and specifically in Erbil city. The researchers came to conclude that non-economic factors are not related to economic growth in Kurdistan region and particularly in private businesses in Erbil City.

KEYWORDS:

Economic factors, Non-economic factors, Economic Growth, Erbil, Kurdistan

INTRODUCTION

Past last two decades the factors of economic growth have concerned growing attention in practical, applied studies, and theoretical. However, the method highlighting economic outcome is ineffectively conceptualized and poorly understood, somewhat, which can be partially recognized to the lack of a universal or unifying factor influencing economic growth.

The most significant matter in economic studies that attracted attention of different domains such as politicians, physicians and economists is economic growth. The reason is the main importance of this topic according to the whole population, which created the sustainability or enhancement of the economic environment (9).

Among academicians, economists and scholars, few of them focused on the topic of determining the economic factors and non-economic factors which are influencing economic growth. Meanwhile development is a very dynamic method, educations that are based on circumstances years ago could not be as related and significant in today's competitive environment. The rapid changes in technological and other factors the last few decades have transformed the way nations enhance their economy. However, this research will assist encourage more studies to gain benefits from determine both economic and non-economic factors and its impact on economic growth (7).

RESEARCH OBJECTIVE AND PURPOSE

The main aim of this study is to investigate both economic and non-economic factors which influence the economic growth of Kurdistan region of Iraq.

Research objectives:

The study has the following objectives:

- To find out the economic factors influencing on economic growth
- To find out the non-economic factors influencing on economic growth
- To examine the correlation between economic factors, non-economic factors with economic growth

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

To meet the research objectives, the researchers set the following research question:

Research question 1- does non-economic factors influence on economic growth of KRG?

Research question2- do economic and non-economic factors influence on economic growth of KRG?

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK**Research model**

Hypothesis 1-: there is a significant and positive impact of demands of products and services on economic growth.

Hypothesis 2-: there is a significant and positive impact of inflation on economic growth.

Hypothesis 3-: there is a significant and positive impact of tax on economic growth.

Hypothesis 4-: there is a significant and positive impact of human resource on economic growth.

Hypothesis 5-: there is a significant and positive impact of technology on economic growth.

Hypothesis 6-: there is a significant and positive impact of political on economic growth.

LITERATURE REVIEW**Economic factors****Demand for products and services**

Economics aspects characterize request as a timetable demonstrating, the measure of specific products and ventures that buyers are eager and ready to purchase at each cost in a lot of conceivable cost amid a predefined time and period. On the off chance that we think likewise that productive use and diminished utilization leads, over the long term, to less power plants fabricated and, in this way, less assets removed and utilized, it is additionally a success for nature and who and what is to come. Demand likewise relies upon purchaser assumptions regarding future changes in the cost. Most stopped lines wind up adroit at making request that coordinates the limit of the quit line to give the administration and the accessibility of the financial backing to support it (15). Subsequently they move effectiveness which we currently measure as a decline in vitality utilization and along these lines; a nonattendance of vitality is really sold. They will incline toward purchasing the ware now when the costs are generally lower interest for the item would along these lines increment. A few organizations changed the degree and view of their branch and now move bundles of effective utilization of vitality and lighting, including data and instruction. Viable advancement ought to produce enough, effective call rates, at a cost proportionate to benefit conveyance costs albeit such advancement ought not animate so much interest that the assets of the framework are overpowered (6). The item where purchasers anticipate that costs should increment sooner rather than later. Interest for an item additionally relies on the extent of the populace. An ideal case of interest side administration is the utility business that was typically considered just as a power provider. Frequently strategy creators think little of the potential reach of quit lines since they compare authentic use with potential use. On the off chance that it would seem that demand will surpass operational limit or spending plan, quit lines may reduce, for instance, on media battles. At the point when populace expands the amount of the item demanded additionally increments. As of now, can see the improvement of interest side administration the focal idea of which is esteem creation for the client and arrangement of the capacity she needs, instead of item or product. The main potential special case to this methodology is if there is a purposeful system to make a mind-boggling demand to urge government officials the requirement for extra subsidizing (13).

Inflation

Inflation is the degree of addition in costs over a specified timeframe. Inflation is usually an expansive measure, for example, the general increment in costs or the inflation in the average cost for basic items in a nation. In creating nations, conversely, swelling is definitely not a simply money related marvel. Adjacent to, factors commonly identified with monetary irregular characteristics, for example, higher cash development and swapping scale deterioration emerging from a parity of installments emergency overwhelm the swelling procedure in creating nations. The reason is that the value development of various products and enterprises are not uniform. Amid inflation, most costs rise, yet the rate of increment of individual costs contrasts (14). As opposed to fiscal focusing on, another conceivable economics approach technique, inflation focusing on has the preferred standpoint that a steady connection among cash and swelling isn't basic to its prosperity: the system does not rely upon such a correlation, but rather utilizes all accessible data to decide the best settings for the instruments of money related strategy. A foundation in this information is fundamental preceding surveying the techniques to and authenticity of dodging such an expense. Whatever the unique situation, swelling speaks to the amount increasingly costly the applicable arrangement of merchandise or potentially benefits have turned out to be over a specific period, most regularly a year. Inflation is, in the meantime, a standout amongst the most feared and a standout amongst the most misconstrued of economics wonders. We know for a fact, joined with meditation, that the costs of products will, after some time, rise and fall, reacting to the pulls and pushes of interest and supply. It is dreaded by national brokers all-inclusive and powers the execution of fiscal arrangements that are intrinsically disliked (4). It makes a few people unreasonably rich and devastates others. This prompts more preservationist speculation systems than would some way or another be the situation, at last prompting lower dimensions of venture and economic development. In any case, it can likewise be all the more barely determined—for specific merchandise, for example, sustenance, or for administrations, for example, a hair style, for instance. It is one of the essential tireless dangers that will undermine or even decimate many years of monetary development whenever released and not checked. Additionally, swelling can result in relative value changes within the sight of ostensible cost and wage rigidities, which can make critical welfare costs. Comprehensively, there are two economics gatherings in each public, the settled pay gathering and the adaptable pay gathering. Inflation is a standout amongst the most oftentimes utilized terms in monetary exchanges, yet the idea is differently misinterpreted. Swelling influences distinctive individuals or monetary specialists in an unexpected way. Inflation focusing on has a few favorable circumstances as a medium-term technique for money related approach. To the degree that cash gives administrations esteemed by buyers and makers, swelling forces a welfare cost. Inflation can prompt vulnerability about the future benefit of speculation ventures (particularly when high swelling is likewise connected with expanded value inconstancy). Amid swelling, those in the principal amass lose while those in the second gathering increase. Inflation focusing on additionally has the key preferred standpoint that it is effortlessly comprehended by people in general and is in this manner very straightforward. Inflation goes about as a duty on cash: high and unstable swelling rates influence contrarily the interest in cash. Firms may need to dedicate more assets to managing the impacts of inflation (for instance, increasingly cautious checking of their rivals' costs to check whether any increments are a piece of a general inflationary pattern in the economy or because of more industry explicit causes) (2). As opposed to a conversion standard peg, inflation focusing on empowers economics arrangement to concentrate on residential contemplations and to react to stuns to the local economy. Swelling may likewise lessen a nation's universal intensity, by making its fares moderately progressively costly, in this way affecting on the parity of installments. As a rule, the reason for swelling in created nations is comprehensively distinguished as development of cash supply. Besides, swelling can collaborate with the assessment framework to mutilate getting and loaning choices. Money related business analysts are particularly appropriate for dissecting swelling as they comprehend the procedure by which it begins and later engenders all through the economy (7).

Tax

Tax is a one of the mainstream points in financial matters. Tax as we probably are aware is a fundamental wellspring of government income and the gathering of the expense. The advancement of endogenous development hypothesis has opened a road through which the impacts of tax on financial development can be investigated. Tax collection of the factor work impacts three central choices made by monetary specialists. Unequivocal demonstrating of the individual choices that add to development permits the investigation of tax occurrence and the expectation of development impacts (1). Changes in tax arrangement, in any case, can produce changes in these harmony esteems, creating passing development impacts. Particularly tax collection of enterprises has extraordinary significance claiming a corporate tax base is a significant versatile factor of

creation and all the while the tax rivalry is as of now still harder because of required financial improvement especially with regards to the monetary emergency. it might misshape the choice to take an interest in the work showcase, i.e. the quantity of working hours and also the quantity of staff employed. As an outcome explore has turned its concentration to increasingly more examination how unique expenses, as opposed to the general tax level, influence monetary conduct. An expansion in the long periods of instruction picked by new participants to the work compel, for instance, will have completely changed the normal training for the work constrain in general simply after the main contestants following the strategy change have achieved retirement age. In any case, unmistakably there has been a solid upward pattern in tax and government spending as an extent of national pay in the created nations in the course of the most recent 50 years. Expense changes are now and again touted as having solid macroeconomic development impacts. This sort of tax may prompt less enterprising action and – therefore – less advancement. As the globalization procedure and universal portability of assets have escalated so has assess rivalry and the weight under which local expense frameworks are put. A standout amongst the most discussed inquiries in economy is the connection between expense rates and monetary development (17). The significance is just elevated by worries about the long-term monetary development rate and worries about the long-term financial status of the government. Diverse ways to deal with the creation and attributes of expense framework with the association with spending issues of created economies underline the hugeness of the issue of common connection between charges (taxation rate) and financial development. Expense consequences for the balance capital stock can likewise set aside some time of opportunity to be felt, because of change expenses to new interest in an open economy or because of the restricted flexibility of reserve funds rates in a shut economy. Firmly dynamic tax collection on pay can have the impact that less market members choose to look for more elevated amounts of instruction. Estimating tax and government spending as an extent of national pay is plagued with troubles. The significance of the themes tended to here get from the pay tax's focal job in income age, its effect on the dissemination of after-charge pay, and its impacts on a wide assortment of monetary exercises (8).

Non-economic factors

Human resources

The investigation of the financial aspects of HR is described by intricacy of the procedures, yet in addition by the factor of specific significance given to HR in ongoing decades. The change of HR today is an immediate call of the fast changes inside organizations because of variables, for example, globalization. As per this idea, the workers in the organization are treated as a standout amongst the most critical resources that an organization has. Organizations with the capacity to predict and economically deal with their workforce needs – particularly for high aptitudes – will pick up the unequivocal upper hand. Undoubtedly, it is unrealistic to introduce every one of the orders and applicable hypothetical angles that have formed the comprehension of human resource the board today. Just a single decade later, notwithstanding, Japan went into a retreat from which it has not yet completely recouped. Incomprehensibly, these equivalent HRM rehearses are presently being seen by a progression of creators as the base of the disquietude. A standout amongst the most critical resources, perhaps the most imperative, in the Greek wellbeing framework is HR (12). HR needs to exploit innovation and information examination to assemble a worldwide human resource data framework that gathers and stores information from different sources. HR alludes to forms that identify with preparing, instruction and other expert activities so as to build the dimensions of information, aptitudes, capacities, qualities, and social resources of a representative which will prompt the worker's fulfillment and execution, and in the long run on a firm execution. This resource, dissimilar to alternate resources is delicate to ecological elements: geographic, social, political and particularly financial. Human resource the executives are viewed as a piece of the administration's circle in the organization and depend on the hypothetical and commonsense information in the field of work brain research. The human advancement approach, in any case, isn't viewed as the most suitable idea to break down the job of ex-soldiers in deactivation and reintegration. HR divisions are changing as the cutting-edge business faces various and complex difficulties, and endeavor openings (3). The framework will break down the information to give business bits of knowledge, foresee future needs and create techniques to fill those necessities. HRM has been seen by numerous eyewitnesses as a key fixing representing the achievement of Japanese organizations on world markets. Administrative view sees HR as a business resource or resource which shapes some portion of the market estimation of the organization. The principle zone of study we will concentrate on will be motivators and work association. Motivators incorporate compensation frameworks and furthermore the arrangement of evaluation, advancement and professional success. In the worldwide rivalry inside the level and associated new world, basic leadership in associations has turned out to be progressively

multifaceted and tangled. The macroeconomic as we can see HR as one of the generation factors, separately wellsprings of the monetary development (Figure 1).

Figure 2-Human Capital

Human asset the executive's standards and strategies for individuals the executives in aggressive associations are drawn from speculations found in various orders. To support aggressiveness in the association HR turns into an instrument used to expand efficiency. The new worldwide world has broadened the ability pool for great and peripheral specialists, and for perpetual and liquid laborers. Moreover, riches aren't the main thing individuals appreciate despite its significance to welfare (14). An association's ability can be a hotspot for a supported upper hand and can influence imperative hierarchical results, for example, survival, productivity, consumer loyalty level, and representative execution. It claims, in any case, that financial development is an important however not an adequate state of human advancement. The idea of Human Resources was first created and advanced in the United States, where the administration as a control originates from. Human advancement does not prevent the significance from claiming financial development and riches gathering for the welfare of society. Along these lines, it is trusted that it is just vital to give the peruse a careless perspective of some important hypotheses supporting human asset the executives and whoever might be keen on find out about the beginning and improvements of an explicit hypothesis may do as such by taking additional homework. While riches may encourage a portion of these wants it isn't, the only one, an adequate factor in such manner. By work association we mean the appropriation of choice rights (self-rule/decentralization) among chiefs and laborers, work structure, group working (e.g. who works with whom) and data arrangement (2). This methodology is viewed as unreasonably wide for the idea of the given undertaking. Moreover, the human improvement approach still faces a few shortcomings at the hypothetical and theoretical dimension. Accordingly, the representatives of the organization are never again seen as an expense to be decreased, yet as a potential wellspring of upper hand, or as partners and accomplices in the acknowledgment of accomplishment. HR the executives is turning into a different order inside the administration that is centered around the investigation and the board of workers in the organization, who, with their very own attributes, information, aptitudes, capacities and by and large mental and physical limits, are one of the key achievement elements of the organization. While the HR and the human asset idea see individuals as methods, the human improvement idea features the double job of individuals both as methods and end of advancement. The expression " HR " has been characterized as a key component in enhancing a firm assets and representatives to increment gainful and additionally support upper hand. Different methods for equivalent significance are the redistribution of profitable assets (specifically arrive change), the redistribution of pay through dynamic financial arrangement, casting a ballot rights changes to even out political chances, foundation of transitory social security nets, and so on. It speaks to an extremely thorough idea in which HR are by all account not the only way to accomplish the human advancement objective (Hartwell,2017).

Technology

Innovative change has for some time been perceived as a critical driver of monetary development. It continues in waves driven by mechanical advancement and dissemination of developments. The center of advancement is concocting the utilization of creation assets in another, prior experienced way and concurrent withdrawal of those assets from current application and use. The significance of data and correspondence advances in monetary and social improvement emerged significantly with high awing position since the beginning of quick development of these innovations and their market in the mid-nineties. Innovation by expecting learning by doing, expressed that it developed at a steady rate, and found that long-run financial development urgently relies upon populace development. Accordingly, a fitting monetary approach should focus on fortifying these procedures all through the nation and facilitating the stream of data and innovation between the primary players – pioneers, organizations, state offices and money related foundations (11). In numerous models of financial development, mechanical change and business elements are between ward. Business elements, including the section and exit of firms, and the reallocation of work through the creation and devastation of employments in various firms, are another critical driver of financial development. Digitization alludes to the changes activated by the huge reception of advanced advances that create, process, and offer and exchange data. Development and innovation exchange are the key drivers of financial development in this day and age economy. In current Schumpeterian development hypothesis new pioneering firms are the vehicle through which new advances enter the market. Early neoclassical models like specialized change as an exogenous variable, delineating to what extent run financial development just relied upon specialized change. The hypothesis in this way predicts a nearby correlation between innovative change and business elements. The connection among innovation and financial development has been caught in countless models for 60 years. Developing economies require an interconnected arrangement of market and nonmarket foundations to make the advancement procedure work viably, and thus, governments require a development methodology on the off chance that they wish to cultivate exceptionally creative monetary frameworks (16). Development is a debilitating and dull action with a high rate of disappointment. Not at all like different advancements driven by a solitary development, has digitization expanded on the advancement of numerous advances. This innovative change delivers an imaginative obliteration of occupant firms, accordingly permitting generation variables to be reallocated to the most productive innovation implanted in the new firms. The quickened advancement of data and correspondence innovation in the course of recent decades has empowered an expanding number of analysts to analyze and gauge the effect of this innovation on financial development. Digitization alludes to the changes activated by the gigantic reception of computerized advances that produce, process, offer and exchange data (12).

Political

Political is viewed by financial analysts as a genuine disquietude destructive to monetary execution. Among legislators, and the business analysts who "murmur in their ears", there is a conviction that popularity-based foundations are useful for development. From one viewpoint, the vulnerability related with an unsteady political condition may lessen venture and the speed of monetary improvement. Although there is no agreement on the effects of majority rules system and dictatorship on monetary development, scenes of high development in a few nations are regularly connected with despotic routines. This how they ought to endeavor please the general individuals and win their help. Political flimsiness is factors that are difficult to gauge in a way which can be utilized in econometric work. Political shakiness includes unsteadiness of governments, routines and networks inside a country. The political gatherings of any nation should stay devoted on working for the social and financial improvement of their nations. Lamentably, while this thought may have great hypothetical and good help, the observational proof for majority rule organizations as an impetus for development is questionable, best case scenario (10). The connection among vote-based system and financial development has gotten impressive consideration as of late. The political condition of a law-based nation can effect on the execution of the national economy from numerous points of view. Up 'til now, be that as it may, there is no accord among examiners on the connection between these two generally contemplated factors. The significance of political security to financial improvement of any nation has turned into a point of a ceaseless discussion among market analysts, political specialists and lawmakers. Political insecurity is probably going to abbreviate policymakers' points of view prompting imperfect transient macroeconomic arrangements (5).

Economic Growth

Economic development can be characterized as the yearly rate increment in all out generation or pay in the economy. Economic growth is the most incredible tool for lessening neediness and enhancing the personal satisfaction in making countries. The dimension of economic advancement offers data about the actualized

political routine, as well as about the tenets and objectives of the individual nation. It is basically an impression gotten from considering the clashing investigations of the issue of misleadingly animating monetary development in the purported immature regions of the world. Industrialization had delivered perpetual changes in the economic and human action. Subsequently, investigating the causes and essential components that lead to a positive economic execution turned into a point of significant enthusiasm for the 21st century researchers (Hartwell,2017). Economic development is the consistent enhancement in the ability to fulfill the interest in merchandise and ventures, coming about because of expanded creation scale, and enhanced efficiency. Economic aspects try to answer these inquiries by building quantitative models—models that can be contrasted and experimental information. The monetary development and advancement have been bantered for a considerable length of time. Scientists and economic specialists reaffirm the requirement for monetary development for the advancement and well been of humankind. Solid development and business openings enhance motivating forces for guardians to put resources into their youngsters' training by sending them to class (3). Monetary development hypotheses and models feature the distinctive manners by which the present economic action can have an effect on future economic advancements and can likewise recognize sources that may prompt proceeded economic development. Development can produce high-minded circles of thriving and opportunity. The procedure of economic development and the wellsprings of contrasts in monetary execution crosswise over countries are the absolute most fascinating, vital and testing regions in present day sociology. Likewise, enhancements in numerical and factual devices have had a huge effect in figuring new ideas. The economic development hypotheses have advanced after some time contingent upon the period and on the elements of economy (11).

METHODOLOGY

The main aim of this study is to investigate both economic and non-economic factors which influence the economic growth of Kurdistan region of Iraq. In order to achieve the aim of this research, the researchers developed a conceptual framework as it can be seen in figure (1), with developed research hypotheses. Moreover, the researchers developed six research hypotheses in order to measure the economic and non-economic factors influencing economic growth in Kurdistan region and specifically in Erbil city. Furthermore, the researchers used two main variables as independent variables in order to measure its dependent variable (economic growth), however each main independent variable have three factors to be measured, these factors are as follow: for economic factors (inflation, tax and demand) factors and for non-economic factors (technology, HR and political) factors to measure economic growth in Kurdistan and especially in Erbil city. For this reason, the researchers applied quantitative research method to measure six research hypotheses, the researchers distributed questionnaires to employees and managers for several private businesses in Erbil city to measure their economic growth. Accordingly, the researchers were able to gather 71 questionnaires all of these questionnaires are valid to be analyzed. The researchers used three separate regression analysis, first multiple regression analysis to measure economic factors (demand, tax and inflation) with economic growth, second step to measure non-economic factors (technology, HR and political) with economic growth and thirdly, economic factors and non-economic factors together with economic growth.

ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

Table 1-Reliability Statistics

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.993	9
Variable	Cronbach's Alpha
Demand	.994
Inflation	.994
Tax	.992
HR	.992
Technology	.994
Political	.992
Economic Growth	.992
Economic factors	.991
Non-economic factors	.992

As we can see in table (1), the reliability statistics for all 9 variables used in this study, the results showed that the value of Alpha = .993 for nine items this means that all variables used to analyze this study are reliable.

Furthermore, as it can be seen in the same mentioned table, each variable with its own alpha, as for demand factors the value of alpha is .994, as for inflation factors the value of alpha is .994, as for tax factors the value of alpha is .992, as for HR factors the value of alpha is .992, as for technology factors the value of alpha is .994, as for political factors the value of alpha is .992, as for economic growth factors the value of alpha is .992, as for economic factors the value of alpha is .991, and as for non-economic factors the value of alpha is .992.

Table 2-Correlation Analysis

		Demand	HR	Tax	Inflation	Technology	Political	Growth
Demand	Pearson Correlation	1						
	Sig. (2-tailed)							
	N	87						
HR	Pearson Correlation	.781**	1					
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000						
	N	87	87					
Tax	Pearson Correlation	.949**	.888**	1				
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000					
	N	87	87	87				
Inflation	Pearson Correlation	.943**	.924**	.968**	1			
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000				
	N	87	87	87	87			
Technology	Pearson Correlation	.802**	.943**	.922**	.922**	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000			
	N	87	87	87	87	87		
Political	Pearson Correlation	.950**	.922**	.972**	.992**	.915**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000		
	N	87	87	87	87	87	87	
Economic Growth	Pearson Correlation	.972**	.880**	.987**	.976**	.909**	.973**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	87	87	87	87	87	87	87

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table (2) shows the correlation analysis between independent variables and dependent variable. The results found that the value of Pearson correlation for demand as economic factor and its correlation with economic growth was .972** , this means that the value is greater than .000 along with 2-tailed and this indicated that there is a significant correlation between demand as economic factor and its correlation with economic growth, the value of Pearson correlation for human resource as non-economic factor and its correlation with economic growth was .880** , this means that the value is greater than .000 along with 2-tailed and this indicated that there is a significant correlation between human resource as non-economic factor and its correlation with economic growth, the value of Pearson correlation for tax as economic factor and its correlation with economic growth was .987** , this means that the value is greater than .000 along with 2-tailed and this indicated that there is a significant correlation between tax as economic factor and its correlation with economic growth, the value of Pearson correlation for inflation as economic factor and its correlation with economic growth was .976** , this means that the value is greater than .000 along with 2-tailed and this indicated that there is a significant correlation between inflation as economic factor and its correlation with economic growth, the value of Pearson correlation for technology as non-economic factor and its correlation with economic growth was .909** , this means that the value is greater than .000 along with 2-tailed and this indicated that there is a significant correlation between technology as non-economic factor and its correlation with economic growth and the value of Pearson correlation for political as non-economic factor and its correlation with economic growth was .973** , this means that the value is greater than .000 along with 2-tailed and this indicated that there is a significant correlation between political as non-economic factor and its correlation with economic growth.

Table 3- Multiple Regression Analysis (Economic Variables)

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Coefficients Beta		
1	(Constant)	.048	.043		1.122	.265
	Demand	.285	.035	.305	8.103	.000
	Tax	.484	.050	.487	9.692	.000
	Inflation	.218	.047	.218	4.595	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Economic Growth

The multiple regression analysis between economic variables and economic growth as seen in the table (3), the results showed that the B value for demand variable as independent variable is .285 with P value of .000 this means that there is a positive correlation between demand and economic growth in Kurdistan region and specifically in Erbil city, this means that the first research hypothesis is supported, the B value for tax variable as independent variable is .484 with P value of .000 this means that there is a positive correlation between tax and economic growth in Kurdistan region and specifically in Erbil city, this means that the second research hypothesis is supported, and the B value for inflation variable as independent variable is .218 with P value of .000 this means that there is a positive correlation between inflation and economic growth in Kurdistan region and specifically in Erbil city, this means that the third research hypothesis is supported.

Table 4-Multiple Regression Analysis (Non-economic Variables)

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Coefficients Beta		
1	(Constant)	.007	.089		.084	.933
	HR	-.318	.074	-.324	-4.288	.009
	Technology	.323	.073	.320	4.415	.000
	Political	.986	.063	.979	15.751	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Economic Growth

The multiple regression analysis between non-economic variables and economic growth as seen in the table (4), the results showed that the B value for HR variable as independent variable is -.318 with P value of .009 this means that there is no a correlation between HR and economic growth in Kurdistan region and specifically in Erbil city, this means that the first research hypothesis is rejected, the B value for technology variable as independent variable is .323 with P value of .000 this means that there is a positive correlation between technology and economic growth in Kurdistan region and specifically in Erbil city, this means that the second research hypothesis is supported, and the B value for political variable as independent variable is .986 with P value of .000 this means that there is a positive correlation between political and economic growth in Kurdistan region and specifically in Erbil city, this means that the third research hypothesis is supported.

Table 5-Multiple Regression Analysis (Economic & Non-economic)

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Coefficients Beta		
1	(Constant)	.004	.058		.075	.941
	Economic	.768	.099	.773	1.819	.000
	Non-economic	-.270	.100	-.263	-2.702	.008

a. Dependent Variable: Economic Growth

The multiple regression analysis between non-economic variables and economic variables with economic growth as seen in the table (5), the results showed that the B value for economic variables is .768 with P value

of .000 this means that there is a strong and positive correlation between economic variables and economic growth in Kurdistan region and specifically in Erbil city, on the other hand, the results showed that the B value for non-economic variables is -.270 with P value of .008 this means that there is no correlation between non-economic variables and economic growth in Kurdistan region and specifically in Erbil city.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We thank our colleagues from Stafford University who provided insight and expertise that greatly assisted the research, although they may not agree with all of the interpretations/conclusions of this paper.

CONCLUSION

The main aim of this study is to investigate both economic and non-economic factors which influence the economic growth of Kurdistan region of Iraq. In order to achieve the aim of this research, the researchers developed a conceptual framework as it can be seen in figure (1), with developed research hypotheses. Moreover, the researchers developed six research hypotheses in order to measure the economic and non-economic factors influencing economic growth in Kurdistan region and specifically in Erbil city. The findings showed that there is a positive correlation between demand and economic growth in Kurdistan region and specifically in Erbil city, there is a positive correlation between tax and economic growth, there is a positive correlation between inflation and economic growth, there is no a correlation between HR and economic growth, there is a positive correlation between technology and economic growth, there is a positive correlation between political and economic growth in Kurdistan region and specifically in Erbil city, this means that the third research hypothesis is supported. Furthermore, comparing non-economic factors and economic factors, the following results found; there is a strong and positive correlation between economic variables and economic growth, on the other hand there is no correlation between non-economic variables and economic growth in Kurdistan region and specifically in Erbil city. The researchers came to conclude that non-economic factors are not related to economic growth in Kurdistan region and particularly in private businesses in Erbil City.

REFERENCES

- [1] Amin, A., Chen, Y., & Huang, S. *Personal Income Tax and Economic Growth: A Comparative Study Between China and Pakistan*. Asian Journal of Economic Modelling, 6(1), 65-73.2018.
- [2] Bittencourt, M., Van Eyden, R., & Seleteng, M. *Inflation and Economic Growth: Evidence from the Southern African Development Community*. South African Journal of Economics, 83(3), 411-424.2015.
- [3] Brata, I. B., & Pemayun, A. G. P. *Human Resource Competency Tourism Bali together with ASEAN Economic Community*. International Research Journal of Management, IT and Social Sciences (IRJMIS), 5(2), 186-194.2018.
- [4] Chu, A. C., Cozzi, G., Furukawa, Y., & Liao, C. H. *Inflation and economic growth in a Schumpeterian model with endogenous entry of heterogeneous firms*. European Economic Review, 98, 392-409.2017.
- [5] Cox, G. W., & Weingast, B. R. *Executive Constraint, Political Stability, and Economic Growth*. Comparative Political Studies, 51(3), 279-303.2018.
- [6] Croes, R., Ridderstaat, J., & van Niekerk, M. *Connecting quality of life, tourism specialization, and economic growth in small island destinations: The case of Malta*. Tourism Management, 65, 212-223.2018.
- [7] Frick, S. A., & Rodríguez- Pose, A. *Big or small cities? On city size and economic growth*. Growth and Change, 49(1), 4-32.2018.
- [8] Hatfield, J. W. *Federalism, taxation, and economic growth*. Journal of Urban Economics, 87, 114-125.2015.
- [9] Isik, C., Dogru, T., & Turk, E. S. *A nexus of linear and non- linear correlations between tourism demand, renewable energy consumption, and economic growth: Theory and evidence*. International

- Journal of
Tourism Research, 20(1), 38-49.2015.
- [10] Li, J., Xia, J., & Zajac, E. J. On the duality of political and economic stakeholder influence on firm innovation performance: Theory and evidence from Chinese firms. *Strategic Management Journal*, 39(1), 193-216.2018.
- [11] Munir, K., & Ameer, A. *Effect of economic growth, trade openness, urbanization, and technology on environment of Asian emerging economies*. *Management of Environmental Quality: An International Journal*, 29(6), 1123-1134.2018.
- [12] Ogundari, K., & Awokuse, T. *Human capital contribution to economic growth in Sub-Saharan Africa: Does health status matter more than education?* *Economic Analysis and Policy*, 58, 131-140.2018.
- [13] Onolemhemhen, R. U., Bello, S. L., & Iwayemi, A. P. *Evaluating the Nexus between Energy Demand and Economic Growth Using the VECM Approach: Case Study of Nigeria, China, and the United States*. *World Academy of Science, Engineering and Technology, International Journal of Social, Behavioral, Educational, Economic, Business and Industrial Engineering*, 11(6), 1601-1606.2017.
- [14] Phiri, A. *Nonlinear impact of inflation on economic growth in South Africa: a smooth transition regression analysis*. *International Journal of Sustainable Economy*, 10(1), 1-17.2018.
- [15] Schubert, S. F., Brida, J. G., & Risso, W. A. *The impacts of international tourism demand on economic growth of a small economy*. *Revista Turismo & Desenvolvimento*, 3(13, 14), 927-928.2017.
- [16] Stanley, T. D., Doucouliagos, H., & Steel, P. *Does ICT Generate Economic Growth? A Meta-Regression Analysis*. *Journal of Economic Surveys*, 32(3), 705-726.2018.
- [17] Thom, M. *Lights, camera, but no action? Tax and economic development lessons from state motion picture incentive programs*. *The American Review of Public Administration*, 48(1), 33-51.2018.